

**A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG HIGHER
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF DARJEELING DISTRICT IN
WEST BENGAL**

Awaneesh Baibhav

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Psychology

Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi

Abstract:

Emotional Intelligence has not traditionally seen the amount of research or exploration that has been given to topics such as cognitive intelligence, mental health and mental capabilities. Since emotion plays a vital role in the ways human interact with each other and perform in home, school and work settings, the need to undertake emotion and Emotional Intelligence is obvious. Emotional Intelligence is the driving force behind the factors that affect personal success and everyday interaction with others. Studies of Emotional Intelligence have shown its relevance of many aspects of life and the role it plays in the interaction and discussions of any given day. Emotional Intelligence predicts as much as 80% of a person's success in life, whereas IQ predicts about 20%. The objective of the study was to study the emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students in relation to gender and type of management variation. Normative survey method was adopted. A sample of 100 students from 4 schools of Darjeeling district was selected by simple random sampling procedure. 'Schutte Self Report Inventory (SSRI)' developed by Schutte et.al. (1998) has been used for assessing Emotional Intelligence of higher secondary school students which consist of 33 items. Findings of the study were that most of the students are emotionally intelligent and there is difference in emotional intelligence in terms of type of management variation.

Key words: Emotional Intelligence, Emotion, IQ

Introduction:

Psychologist Mayer, et al. (1989) coined the term Emotional Intelligence, though it was referred by various names - from smartness and personality to soft skills and competence. Emotional Intelligence contains two major aspects “Emotions” and “Intelligence”. Emotion is as any agitation or disturbance of mind, passion, any achievement or excited mental state. Emotions or feelings have both a psychological component and cognitive element that influence behavior. Intelligence is the capacity to understand the word, think rationally and use resources effectively when faced with challenges. Emotional Intelligence refers to the ability required for efficient living.

The term emotional intelligence has been rooted from the social intelligence, which was first coined by EL Thorndike in 1920. In 1985, Reuven Bar-on invented the term Emotional Quotient (E.Q i.e. E.Q is a relative measure of one’s emotional intelligence possessed by him at a particular period of his life) to describe his approach to evaluating general intelligence. In the first time Peter Salovey of Yale and John Mayer of University of New Hampshire (1990) conceptualized the term Emotional Intelligence that consisted of three different categories of adaptive abilities. Firstly, it is appraisal and expression in the self as well as others. In the self there are verbal and non-verbal components, in the others there are non-verbal perception and empathy. Secondly there is regulation of emotion in the self and others. Thirdly, it is utilization of emotion that includes flexible planning, redirected attention and motivation. Daniel Goleman (1995) and American psychologist then subsumed this definition with a lot of personality characteristics, which he believed would contribute positively to success in any domain of life. Goleman (1999) Emotional Intelligence encompasses the following five characteristics and abilities.

Personal Competence: - These competencies determine how we manage ourselves.

Self-awareness: Knowing what we are feeling in the moment and using those preferences to guide our decision making, having a realistic assessment of our own abilities and a well - grounded sense of self – confidence. Emotional awareness – Recognizing one’s emotions and their effect. Accurate

Self-assessment – Knowing one’s strengths and limits. Self – confidence: A strong sense of one’s self – worth and capabilities.

Self-Regulation (moods managements): Managing one’s internal states, impulses and resources.

Self-control: Keeping disruptive emotions and Band integrity. Conscientiousness: taking responsibility for personal performance. Adaptability: Flexibility in handling change. Innovation: Being comfortable with novel ideas, approaches and new information.

Self-Motivation: Emotional tendencies that guide or facilitate reaching goals. Achievements drive: Aligning with the goals of the groups or organization. Initiative: Readiness to act on opportunities. Optimism: Persistence in pursuing goals despite obstacles and setbacks.

Social Competence: These competencies determine how we handle relationships.

Empathy: Awareness of others feeling needs and concerns. Understanding others: Sensing others feeling and perspective, and taking an active interest in their concerns. Developing others: Sensing others development needs and bolstering their abilities. Service Orientation: Anticipating, recognizing and meeting customer’s needs. Leveraging diversity: Cultivating opportunities through different kinds of people. Political awareness: Reading a group emotional currents and power relationships.

Social Skills: (Managing relationships): Adeptness at inducing desirable response in others. Influence: Wielding effective tactics for persuasion. Communication: Listening openly and sending convincing messages. Conflict Managements: Negotiating and resolving disagreements. Leadership: Inspiring and guiding individuals and groups. Change catalyst: Initiating or managing change. Building bounds: Nurturing instrumental relationship. Collaboration and co – operation: Working with others toward shared goals. Team capabilities: Creating group synergy in pursuing collective goals.

Reviews of Related Literature:

Bhat, A.A. (2017) conducted a study on “Emotional Intelligence of Higher Secondary School Students with Respect to their gender”. The objectives of the study were to find out the level of

emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students in Baramulla and to find out the level of emotional intelligence with respect to their gender. The sample of the study consisted 120 students from different higher secondary schools of Baramulla district in Jammu and Kashmir. Emotional Intelligence scale (EIS) developed by Anukool Hyde, Sanjyot Pethe and Upinder Dhar was used for data collection and collected data was analyzed using Mean, SD, Analysis of Variance and 't'-test. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in Emotional Intelligence in relation to gender which meant that girls had more emotional intelligence rather than boys.

Bharadwaz, D and Hussain, R (2020) conducted a study on “Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School Students with special reference to Kamrup (M) district of Assam”. The objectives of the study were to find out the level of emotional intelligence of secondary school students and to compare the emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to their gender. The sample of the study included 156 students from 4 secondary schools of Guwahati, Kamrup District (M) in Assam. Emotional Intelligence Inventory (EII) 2004 by Dr S.K. Mangal and Shubhra Mangal was used to collect data and the obtained data was analyzed using percentage, Mean, Median, Standard deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis and t-test. The findings of the study revealed that most of the secondary school students fall under average level of emotional intelligence.

Kumar, M (2020) conducted a study on “Emotional Intelligence of Higher Secondary School Students”. The objective of the study was to find out the emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students in relation to gender, subject, locality of the school, type of family, father's occupation, and family income. The sample of the study included 300 students from three different higher secondary schools. Emotional Intelligence Quotient tool by Dr. Reuven baron was used for data collection and for analyzing the data Mean, Standard deviation and 't- test were used. The findings of the study revealed that emotional intelligence was independent of gender, subject, locality of the school, type of family, father's occupation, and family income. It was found that the

level of higher secondary school student's emotional intelligence was average in nature and the female students were found to be better than the male students on their emotional intelligence.

Mali, P (2022) conducted a study on "Emotional Intelligence of Higher Secondary Students –A study in Kamrup District". The objectives of the study were to measure emotional intelligence of higher secondary students and to find out a significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary students from urban and rural area, also to find out a significant difference in emotional intelligence of the higher secondary students from joint and nuclear family. The sample of the study included 600 higher secondary school and college students from urban and rural areas in Kamrup district. Emotional Intelligence Inventory by Dr. S.K Mangal and Mrs. Shubhra Mangal was used for data collection and obtained data was analyzed using Mean, S.D. and 't'-test. The findings of the study indicated that the level of EI of rural H.S students was higher than the urban H.S students and a significant difference was found in EI score of H.S students from joint and nuclear family.

Singh, M and Thapa, P (2023) conducted a study on "Emotional Intelligence of Higher Secondary School Students in the District of Kalimpong". The Objectives of the study were to study the Emotional Intelligence of Higher Secondary School Students in terms of gender, types of school and types of management. The sample of the study included 300 higher secondary school students. The data was collected using Emotional Intelligence Inventory (EII) 2004 by Dr S.K. Mangal and Shubhra Mangal. The collected data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics such as Mean, SD, and t-test. The findings of the study indicated that there was no significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of higher secondary school students in terms of gender. There was also a significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of higher secondary school students in relation to types of schools and types of management.

Geetha, B and Sharath Kumar, C. R. (2023) conducted a study on "Emotional Intelligence among Secondary School Students". The objectives of this study were to assess the level of

Emotional Intelligence among secondary school students and to find out the significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of secondary school students in relation to gender and locale. The sample of the study included 90 students from different types of high school (rural and urban) of Mysuru district in Karnataka. Emotional intelligence scale by Ankul Hyde, Sanjyot Pethe and Upinder Dhar (English) was used for data collection and obtained data was analyzed using Mean, Standard deviation, Percentile analysis and 't'-test. The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school students with respect to their Emotional Intelligence and also found that there was a significant difference in Emotional intelligence of secondary school students in relation to gender and their urban locality.

Rationale of the study:

Emotional Intelligence can enable teacher to resolve past issues and both external as well as internal conflicts, help them to attain emotional power and accomplish their goals at all levels physical, mental, spiritual and emotional and also improve psychological abilities such as memory, clarity of thinking and decision- making.

Emotional Intelligence is a primary factor in healthy ageing permitting the human being to live long as well and it is positively impact to the individual ability to sustain both mental and physical health. Emotional Intelligence also enables to assume responsibility for an individual's feeling by saying "I feel" instead of "I should not have".

Emotional Intelligence helps in stimulating motivation, improving communication, reducing stress and enhancing decision – making power of teachers, administrators, students and also parents. Emotional Intelligence also helps to cope with stressful situations stress managements, therefore large by depends upon striking an emotional balance between a potential stress condition and reaction to it. So, the present study intends to study the Emotional Intelligence of higher secondary school students.

While doing the research, the researcher tried to answer the following queries.

- Is there any significant difference in emotional intelligence of students of higher secondary schools in relation to gender variation?
- Is there any significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students in relation to type of management variation?

Therefore, the problem is stated as “A study on Emotional Intelligence among higher secondary school students of Darjeeling district in West Bengal”.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To assess the level of Emotional Intelligence of Higher Secondary School Students of Darjeeling District.
2. To find out the significant difference in emotional intelligence of students of higher secondary schools in relation to gender variation.
3. To find out the significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students in relation to type of management variation.

Hypotheses of the Study:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students in relation to gender variation.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students in relation to type of management variation.

Methodology:

The Design: Normative survey method was adopted in the present research to obtain pertinent information concerning the area of the study. Hence, this method of ex-post facto type in nature and content was used in this study.

Sample: A sample of 100 students from 4 schools of Darjeeling district was selected by simple random sampling procedure.

Tools used for the Study: ‘Schutte Self Report Inventory (SSRI)’ developed by Schutte et.al. (1998) has been used for assessing Emotional Intelligence of higher secondary school students which consist of 33 items.

Analysis and Interpretation of data: Hypotheses testing

Under this subsection attempts were made by the investigator to interpret the data in terms of the objectives and hypotheses formulated earlier. For this the sample was split into two sub-samples namely: Boy Vs Girl and Private Vs Government Schools, In order to make a statistical comparison the ‘t’ ratios were calculated in all the cases and the results were presented in each and every cases. For determining the significance of difference between the means and variances of each of the contrasts the ‘t’ ratios were calculated and tested for significance at 0.05 level and 0.01 level of significance and depending upon the result, the hypotheses were rejected or accepted. The corroboration of earlier studies was made with regard to the result and interpretation was made accordingly. The details of this were presented below.

Analysis of Emotional Intelligence of Students in Relation to Gender Variation:

In order to test to test the gender difference in emotional intelligence of student’s ‘t’ ratio had been calculated and presented below:

Table 1: Test of significance of difference on Emotional Intelligence of students due to gender variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	't'	Remark
Gender	Boy	50	109.46	30.36	5.98	1.18	NS
	Girl	50	116.56	29.45			

P values of t at 0.05 level= 1.98, 0.01 level= 2.63 for df 98, NS refers to Not Significant

It was quite evident from the above table that the obtained value of 't' ratio was 1.18 which was smaller than the table value 0.05 level= 1.98, 0.01 level= 2.63. Hence the 't' ratio (1.18) in case of gender variation was not significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level and we may conclude that there was no significant difference between boy and girl in their emotional intelligence. The result was in the conformity with the earlier studies done by Sivakumar (2010) who found there is no significant difference between boys and girls on emotional intelligence.

Analysis of Emotional Intelligence of Students in Relation to Type of Management Variation:

In order to test to test the type of management difference in emotional intelligence of student's 't' ratio had been calculated and presented below:

Table 2: Test of significance of difference on Emotional Intelligence of students due to type of management variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	't'	Remark
Type of Management	Private	50	116.52	31.04	5.98	1.17	NS
	Government	50	109.5	28.75			

It was quite evident from the above table that the obtained value of 't' ratio was 1.17 which was smaller than the table value 0.05 level= 1.98, 0.01 level= 2.63. Hence the 't' ratio (1.17) in case of

type of management variation was not significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level and we may conclude that there was no significant difference in their emotional intelligence due to type of management difference. The result was in the conformity with the earlier studies done by John Louis and Doss (2007) who found that there does not exist any difference due to type of management variation.

Category in accordance with the level of Emotional Intelligence:

The scores were then calculated as per the conditions of normality in respect of inclusion of percentages of cases within +- 16 limits, +-26 limits and +-36 limits. In order to categories the students in different levels of Emotional Intelligence. These limits were considered for this the number of samples was categorized under five heads and their score ranges were calculated along with the number of students contained in those limits. The same has been presented in table 3.

Table 3: Category in accordance with the level of Emotional Intelligence

	Limits of Raw Score	Number of Students
High	78 & above	0
Above average	70-77	18
Average	50-70	63
Below average	45-55	18
Poor	44 & below	01

On perusal of the above table, it was revealed that the score on Emotional Intelligence has not been obtained in the right direction might have been due to the fact that the sample is very small and the assumed that the skewness of the curve being -0.27 it approached almost normality. In view of the above the investigator desires to conclude that the result obtained in the study may be treated as appropriate and a normal.

Findings of the study:

- From the result it was found that most of the students are emotionally intelligent. Findings also showed that there is no difference in emotional intelligence in terms of gender variation.
- The distribution is normal distribution.
- Type of management variation also did not play any vital role in the emotional intelligence of the students.

Recommendations:

The present study highlights the level of emotional intelligence among students across gender and type of management variation. In the school, colleges and / or universities the teacher play role to improve EQ among the students by providing adequate environmental activity-based example and illustrations in the class. The Teacher should acknowledge accept and emphases with the feeling of their students. They should create the salubrious environment for the students in a positive way and direct them to think of all possible solutions of their own way. In work place and elsewhere with the improvement of interpersonal relationship among students and/or persons who are related to that works or situations and / or persons who are related, to that work or situation IQ can be nurtured by them. In adolescent stage to avoid loneliness, Lacks of concentration, being stubborn, drug abuse, feeling unsolved and many more problems emotional intelligence concept should be introduced in all level of education system.

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